

Notes

Stepwise Stability Constants of Indium(III) Complexes with Salicylic and Anthranilic Acid : A Polarographic Study

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THE complexing tendency of Salicylic acid and Anthranilic acid with various transition metal ions is well known¹. Sarin and Munshi^{2,3} have reported the stepwise formation constants for Indium(III) complexes with hydroxy and amino substituted analogs of succinic acid and propionic acid, using potentiometric and pH metric techniques.

Polarographic studies⁴ of Indium(III) complexes of some amino acids have been reported. An up to date survey of literature reveals that the polarographic studies on the Indium(III) complexes with Salicylic acid and Anthranilic acid have not been made. The present study was undertaken to investigate the composition and stability constants of complexes by making a Deford-Hume⁶ treatment of the observed polarographic data.

Experimental

Indium nitrate (Schuchardt Munchen Germany) solution was prepared in 0.2 M perchloric acid medium and was standardised using PAN indicator⁵.

The ligand solutions were prepared in 75% v/v aqueous ethanol media by using Salicylic acid and Anthranilic acid of B.D.H. grade.

The pH of the test solutions was kept constant at 5.0 using potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.2 by the addition of appropriate amount of sodium perchlorate.

An automatic pen recording C I C. (Baroda, India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. A Philips pH meter was used to measure the pH of the test solutions. Pure hydrogen was passed through the solutions before recording the polarograms. All the measurements were made at the room temperature $27 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Indium(III) gives a well defined reversible, three electron reduction wave in 0.2 M sodium perchlorate

supporting electrolyte in presence of $2.5 \times 10^{-5} M$ potassium hydrogen phthalate at pH 5.0. The nature of the wave is diffusion controlled. A similar behaviour was observed for Indium(III) in complex forms. The value of half-wave potential for Indium(III) at this pH is -0.58 volts vs SCE.

On gradual increase of ligand concentration the half-wave potential shifted to more negative value in both the cases (Indium(III) salicylate and Indium(III) anthranilate systems). A Deford-Hume⁶ treatment of the data reveals the formation of 1:1 Indium(III) salicylate complex and 1:1 and 1:2 Indium(III) anthranilate complexes. The values of stability constants are given below :

Complex	M:L	Stability Constants
In(III) Salicylate	1:1	$\log \beta_1 = 2.5$
In(III) Anthranilate	1:1	$\log \beta_1 = 5.0$
In(III) Anthranilate	1:2	$\log \beta_2 = 4.5$

This difference in stability constants of the complexes of salicylic acid and anthranilic acid may be explained on the basis of the mesomeric effect in anthranilic acid which causes a decrease in proton affinity of NH_2 group which is responsible for the increase of metal ligand stability constants.

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